

DELIVERABLE D3.3

Semi-industrial pilot scale Si-production

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1 INTRODUCTION AND SUMMARY

Work package 3 (WP3), led by Northern Silicon (NOSI), is aiming to develop a pilot-plant for production of PV-silicon from secondary raw materials, which may include kerf, pot scrap, silica crucibles and graphite from the CZ-pullers. The objectives of this work package are:

- To re-introduce Si-kerf, graphite, and silica waste products to the silicon value chain through the NOSI silicon process.
- Develop agglomeration and pre-treatment methods for the waste materials to make them suitable for charging to furnaces in terms of purity and material handling.
- Develop proper recipes for mixtures of virgin and secondary material as well as process modification for Si production and refining.
- Build and operate industrial scale a demonstrator for the entire value chain from silicon waste to Si-metal.

WP3 includes four main tasks:

- T3.1: Upscaling and demonstration of economical method for raw materials purification and agglomeration pre-treatment
- T3.2: Demonstration of Si-production
- **T3.3: Upscaling and demonstration of economical method for melt-treatment/ directional solidification /return to PV value chain**
- T3.4: Upscaling and demonstration of complete kerf to silicon method in large scale

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this report is to present a public report on the work done in task **T3.3: Upscaling and demonstration of economical method for melt-treatment/ directional solidification /return to PV value chain**. This task is divided into two main parts:

- Summary of the waste streams of crucibles, pot scrap and kerf, their expected abundance in the future, purity and the pre-treatment method needed before it can be considered a raw material.
- Silicon production by SAF, smelting by plasma and refining by directional solidification.

1.2 List of definitions acronyms and abbreviations

TABLE 1: ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CB	Carbon black
CZ	Czochralski
ICARUS-briquettes	Briquettes with C/SiO ₂ mole ratio close to 3 with pot-scrap
ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
GDMS	Glow Discharge Mass Spectroscopy
kerf	Sawing dust from the wafer sawing process
mc-Si	Multicrystalline silicon
NoSi	Northern Silicon
NoSi-briquettes	Briquettes with C/SiO ₂ mole ratio close to 3 with virgin quartz-sand
PV	Photo Voltaic
SAF	Submerged Arc Furnace
WP	Work Package

1.3 Structure

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 gives an overview of the waste streams, crucibles, pot scrap and kerf, their abundance and expected abundance, purity, and briquetting development.
- Section 3 describes three different routes for reintroducing the waste streams back in the PV value chain:
 - Silicon production from crucible, pot scrap and kerf by SAF,
 - Smelting of kerf by plasma and
 - Silicon refining by directional solidification in a multicrystalline silicon process and by Czochralski-pulling.

1.4 Relationship with other documents

This document complements and extracts a public summary from the following deliverables:

- D3.1 Agglomeration of Si-kerf, silica, and graphite
- D3.2 Si-production screening experiments
- D3.4 Industrial pilot scale Si-production

This document also uses input from the following deliverables:

- D1.3 Intermediate waste inventory
- D2.8 Technological advances on the treatment of Si-kerf, graphite, and silica waste streams from the PV industry
- D6.18 Pilot-scale trails for multi-silicon ingot growth
- D6.19 Pilot-scale trails for mono-silicon ingot growth

2 RAW MATERIALS

2.1 Amounts and predictions

2.1.1 Si Kerf

The estimated global cumulative Si kerf generation is shown in Figure 1. The silicon wafer production volume has been used to calculate the kerf generated during the wafering process. The estimation of Si kerf includes the consideration annual PV installations, PV production to installation ratio, crystalline PV production volume and cell to wafer ratio. According to the estimation the generated Si kerf from the wafering process in 2023 is around 322 006 tons which is equivalent to 22% of the polysilicon consumption. Apart from the wafering process, the Si kerf is generated also during the cropping, squaring, chamfering, and grinding processes which accounts for 4.5% of the poly-Si consumption¹. In 2020, the slight dip in annual kerf generation was due to the market shift from multi to mono. According to the PV installations and its forecast (2018 to 2027), the cumulative Si kerf generated at the end of 2027 would have reached around 3 472,5 kMT, see Table 2.

FIGURE 1: CUMULATIVE SI KERF GENERATION (CUMULATIVE: 2018-2027) IN PV INDUSTRIES

¹ P. Brailovsky, K. Baumann, M. Held, A.K. Briem, K. Wambach, E. Gervais, S. Herceg, B. Mertvoy, S. Nold, J. Rentsch, Insights into circular material and waste flows from c-Si PV industry, EPJ Photovoltaics 14 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjpv/2022029>.

TABLE 2: GLOBAL SI KERF GENERATION IN PV INDUSTRIES

Year	Polysilicon feed consumption (kMT)	Annual Si kerf generation from Diamond wire saw (kMT)	Cropping, squaring, Chamfering kerf loss (4.5% from poly-Si feed) (kMT)	Annual kerf generation (kMT)	% from Poly-Si feed	Cumulative Kerf Generation (kMT)
2018	431.3	111.5	19.4	130.9	30.34%	130.9
2019	488.9	122.5	22.0	144.5	29.56%	275.4
2020	491.4	107.7	22.1	129.8	26.42%	405.2
2021	658.3	138.9	29.6	168.5	25.60%	573.7
2022	933.4	201.0	42.0	243.0	26.04%	816.8
2023	1464	322.0	65.9	387.9	26.49%	1204.7
2024	1661	368.9	74.7	443.6	26.71%	1648.3
2025	1840	423.5	82.8	506.3	27.52%	2154.6
2026	2204	514.9	99.2	614.1	27.86%	2768.7
2027	2466	592.8	111.0	703.8	28.54%	3472.5

According to the estimation, the percentage of Si kerf generation is around 25 to 30% of the total poly silicon consumption. The emergence of mono and diamond wire cutting has resulted in the lower % of Si kerf generation in 2020 and 2021. However, continuous reduction in specific poly-Si consumption and wafer thickness has slightly increased the % of kerf loss after 2021.

- **Si Kerf Generation in EU:**

According to the EU target of 30GW², the Si kerf generation in EU have been estimated for four different scenarios as shown in Table 3. According to reports^{3 4}, the efficiency of the mono PERC cells will reach more than 24.5% and the TOPCon n type cells would reach around 26.5% by 2030. The kerf loss would reach less than 47 μm by 2030. The annual kerf generation has been estimated for four different scenarios considering two different efficiencies (24.5% and 26.5%) and kerf losses (45 μm and 55 μm) as shown in the table. It was assumed that the efficiency and kerf loss in 2030 would be between the values chosen to estimate the kerf in four different scenarios. According to which, the 30 GW of wafer production would lead to generation Si kerf in between 15 626.15 tons to 19 800.89 tons per year which is 26% to 33% of the polysilicon requirement for 30 GW capacity if it is considered that 2 000 MT poly-Si consumption per GW. The scenario of EU not reaching the target has not been included in this work.

² The current state of the EU photovoltaic industry An in-depth look at the ingot-wafer supply chain, Final report summarizing the findings of interviews conducted for the supply chain gap study. Fraunhofer-Institut für Solare Energiesysteme ISE, 2024.

³ Johannes Bernreuter, The Polysilicon Market Outlook 2027, BERNREUTER RESEARCH Polysilicon Market Reports.

⁴ L. Oberbeck, K. Alvino, B. Goraya, M. Jubault, IPVF's PV technology vision for 2030, Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications 28 (2020) 1207–1214. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.3305>.

TABLE 3: SI KERF ESTIMATION FOR 30GW CAPACITY

2030		I	II	III	IV
wafer length	mm	210	210	210	210
wafer diagonal	mm	295	295	295	295
Wafer thickness	µm	130	130	130	130
Avg cell efficiency	%	26.5	24.5	26.5	24.5
Cell power	W	11.69	10.8	11.69	10.8
Production	GW	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00
Total no of cells		2,566,295,97	2,777,777,778	2,566,295,97	2,777,777,77
Cell to wafer ratio	%	109.00%	109.00%	109.00%	109.00%
Total no of wafers		2,797,262,61	3,027,777,778	2,797,262,61	3,027,777,77
kerf loss	µm	45	45	55	55
kerf loss/ wafer	g	4.621	4.621	5.648	5.648
kerf loss	tons	12,926.15	13,991.36	15,798.94	17,100.89
Other kerf losses (4.5% of 60kMT Poly-Si)	tons	2700.0	2700.0	2700.0	2700.0
Total Kerf Loss	tons	15,626.15	16,691.36	18,498.94	19,800.89
kerf loss/day	tons	42.81	45.73	50.68	54.25

2.1.2 Crucibles and pot scrap

The transition from growing 1 ingot/crucible to growing 6 to 8 ingots/crucible, known as rechargeable Cz process/multi-pulling, significantly reduced the crucible consumption, downtime, and energy consumption. Further improvements such as larger crucibles, longer ingots, efficient insulation of hot-zone, higher pull speed have led to increased productivity. The estimation was done assuming that the ingots are grown by multi batch pulling and for making M10 and G12 size wafers. The market share of G1 and M6 wafers has shrunken due to the emergence of large size M10 and G12 wafers and it is expected that the M10 and G12 will be dominating the PV market for the next 5 to 10 years.

According to recent developments, 65 to 75 pullers need to be operated for 1 GW capacity. Each puller would contribute 14 to 16 MW⁵. Recently the recommended crucible hot hour is 400 hrs and it is expected to extend to 500 hrs. However, the emergence of n type ingot growth has lowered the crucible lifetime to 350 hrs. The downtime between each run is around 6 hours. If it is considered 406 hours per run, 22 runs per puller can be done, meaning it requires 22 crucibles per puller per year. For 1 GW, if it is considered that there are 75 pullers, it required 1 618 crucibles per year. For 610 GW, it requires 987 118 crucibles per year and for 30GW it requires

⁵ The current state of the EU photovoltaic industry An in-depth look at the ingot-wafer supply chain, Final report summarizing the findings of interviews conducted for the supply chain gap study. Fraunhofer-Institut für Solare Energiesysteme ISE, 2024.

45 547 crucibles per year. The crucible weight varies depending on the supplier. Usually for the growth of M10 or G12 size crystal, 36" or 37" crucibles are used which weigh around 85 to 90 kg. According to which the global PV industries would have produced 88 841 MT of crucible waste in 2023. According to the EU's target of 30 GW, it will produce around 4 369 MT of crucible waste each year. Figure 2 shows the projection of world wide crucible waste from 2023 to 2027. According to⁶, there would be 25000 crucibles need to be produced for 15GW capacity and according to our calculation the crucible consumption for 15 GW capacity is around 24 273. The pot scrap at the end of each run would currently be around 5 to 10 kg. According to this 1 618 crucibles/GW would produce around 16.18 tons of pot scrap and it would be around 486 tons for 30 GW capacity. The pot scarp projection is shown in Figure 3 and the details have been given in Table 4.

TABLE 4: ESTIMATION OF CRUCIBLE WASTE GENERATION IN PV INDUSTRIES

No of pullers for 1GW (65 to 75)	75	
Capacity of one puller	13.33	MW
Max Crucible heat time	400	hrs
Down time	6	hrs
Total hrs/run	406	
Total Crucibles/puller/year	22	
For 75 Pullers	1618	crucibles
Pot Scrap/GW	16.2	Tons
Pot Scrap 30 GW	486	Tons
No of Crucibles: 610 GW	987118	crucibles
No of Crucibles: 30 GW	48547	crucibles
Weight of 36" Crucible	90	kg
Total Crucible waste in 2023 (610 GW)	88841	MT
Total Crucible waste/year for 30 GW	4369	MT

⁶ PV Manufacturing in Europe: understanding the value chain for a successful industrial policy, 2023.

FIGURE 2: GLOBAL CRUCIBLE WASTE GENERATION IN PV INDUSTRIES

FIGURE 3: GLOBAL POT SCRAP GENERATION IN PV INDUSTRIES

2.1.3 Graphite

The hot zone materials are made of different kinds of graphite. There are more than 50 components in the hot zone, such as isostatic graphite, graphite felt, hard felt, graphite soft felt. Hot zones have a very complicated setup. According to⁷, the 30 GW PV integrated value chain roughly needs 3000 tons of graphite consumptions. Figure 4 has been plotted assuming that the graphite consumption/GW is 100 Tons. For 30 GW capacity, it would produce 3000 Tons of graphite waste. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the overall waste generation and its proportion.

⁷ The current state of the EU photovoltaic industry An in-depth look at the ingot-wafer supply chain, Final report summarizing the findings of interviews conducted for the supply chain gap study. Fraunhofer-Institut für Solare Energiesysteme ISE, 2024

FIGURE 4: PROJECTION OF GLOBAL GRAPHITE WASTE GENERATION IN PV INDUSTRIES

FIGURE 5: GLOBAL WASTE PROJECTION IN 2023

FIGURE 6: WASTE PROJECTION FOR 30GW CAPACITY

2.2 Analysis

The analysis of silicon kerf and pot scrap is important for their effective recycling into the PV value chain. This process involves identifying potential contamination sources and conducting impurity analysis to ensure the materials meet the required quality standards. This is usually done using LECO analysis (for carbon and oxygen content) and ICP-MS (for trace elements) for silicon kerf, and XRF for pot scrap, detailed compositional insights can be obtained. Table 5 summarizes the potential contamination sources and impurities of silicon kerf and pot scrap. Detailed information can be found in D1.4 (Public Intermediate Waste Inventory).

TABLE 5: OVERVIEW OF POTENTIAL CONTAMINATIONS SOURCES OF WASTE PRODUCTS AND THEIR IMPURITIES

Material	Potential contamination source	Impurity
Silicon kerf	Steel wire with electroplated nickel coating and diamonds	Iron, nickel, and carbon
	Wire spools	Aluminum
	Beam holding the silicon brick	Aluminum tri-hydroxide, polymethyl methacrylate
	Adhesive bonding (beam/silicon brick)	Epoxy based adhesives, organic compounds
	Cutting fluid	Organic compounds, surfactants, water
	Filtration aid	Diatomaceous earth (80-90% silica, 2-4% alumina, 0.5-2% iron oxide)
	Silicon dopants and impurities	Boron, phosphorous, gallium, carbon and oxygen
Pot scrap	Devitrification agent/coating	Barium and other alkaline-earth metals
	Crucible impurities	Aluminum and others
	Chemical reactions	silicon droplets

Presented here is the LECO analysis of the silicon kerf sample RST-SONG3, used in the SAF campaigns III and IV, as an example. This analysis was conducted on three silicon kerf samples from the same batch to determine the carbon (C) and oxygen (O) content. The results, summarized in Table 6, show that the average carbon content in the RST-SONG3 kerf sample is 1.21 wt.%, while the oxygen content is 4.44 wt.%.

TABLE 6: LECO ANALYSIS OF RST-SONG3

Samples	C (wt%)	O (wt%)
1	1.25	4.49
2	1.25	4.38
3	1.12	4.44
Avg.	1.21	4.44
Std.	0.08	0.05

Similarly, ICP-MS analysis was conducted to measure the impurity content in the same kerf sample. The results of this analysis are shown in Figure 7. As seen in the figure, phosphorus (P) is the primary dopant impurity present in higher concentrations. Additionally, calcium (Ca) is the metallic contaminant with the highest concentration.

FIGURE 7: ICP-MS ANALYSIS FOR RST-SONG3

In a similar manner, the pot scrap used in SAF campaigns III and IV was analyzed using XRD analysis. The results from this analysis are shown in Figure 8. The analysis indicates three main phases in the pot scrap sample: silicon metal, SiO₂ cristobalite, and amorphous SiO₂, comprising 16%, 2%, and 82% respectively.

FIGURE 8: XRD ANALYSIS: FITTING FOR SILICON, AMORPHOUS PHASE, AND CRISTOBALITE

2.3 Briquetting

One method of re-introducing recycled PV waste back into the PV value chain is through the agglomeration process, specifically using the briquetting process. Briquetting is an efficient and effective method when it is required to utilize these recycled materials for the carbothermic reduction of silica in a Submerged Arc Furnace (SAF). For this purpose, quartz source material, such as pot scrap, and carbon source material, such as pure carbon black or graphite, are agglomerated into self-reducing briquettes. These briquettes are then used in the SAF for silicon production.

In this work package, powdered pot scrap is combined with carbon black to make self-reducing briquettes for use in SAF campaigns III and IV, using the DMSMAC briquetting machine shown in Figure 9. Similarly, kerf briquettes made entirely from silicon kerf and binders were produced using the same machine. Both types of briquettes were successfully used to produce silicon in the SAF furnace campaigns.

FIGURE 9: DMSMAC BRIQUETTING MACHINE

The recycling of waste materials through briquetting process involves several important steps as summarized in Figure 10.

FIGURE 10: BRIQUETTING PROCESS

1. Collection and pre-treatment of recycled materials

Various recycled materials, including pot scrap and silicon kerf, are first collected from different stages of the PV value chain. These materials then undergo a pretreatment stage, which may include washing, crushing, milling, and the removal of impurities and surface contaminants. Once the required material quality is achieved, the materials are either used in the agglomeration process or directly in the SAF furnace to produce silicon.

2. Agglomeration recipe:

The pre-agglomeration process involves preparing a mixture based on specific properties and requirements. In this work package, the task included adjusting the initial recipes to include as

much secondary (recycled) materials as possible without compromising the quality of the agglomerates. The reference mixture consisted of pure quartz sand and carbon black as the main components. The goal was to replace the quartz with pot scrap and the carbon black with recycled graphite without affecting the reactivity of the briquettes. Similarly, part of the task was to find the optimal agglomerate mixture recipe for silicon kerf. The selected agglomeration materials are then mixed with a binder and water.

3. Briquetting:

This step involves compacting the agglomerated mixture using a briquetting machine, where the materials are compressed under high pressure to form briquettes. This process is crucial as it determines the density and mechanical integrity of the briquettes. It is important that the briquettes possess adequate mechanical strength to withstand the rigors of being charged into the SAF furnace without breaking. Once the green briquettes are made, it is important for them to undergo a heat treatment process to improve their mechanical strength and reduce moisture content. This process involves drying the green briquettes in an oven at 105 °C for 12-24 hours, followed by a subsequent heating at 200 °C for another 12-24 hours.

4. Quality control:

After briquetting and heat treatment, the briquettes undergo quality control and testing to ensure they meet the required quality for use in the SAF. This includes drop tests, compression tests, SiC formation tests, and SiO reactivity tests. The drop and compression tests are crucial to ensure that the briquettes possess the necessary mechanical strength to withstand mechanical stress throughout various stages, from the briquetting machine to the base of the SAF furnace. The briquettes face potential risks of disintegration at multiple points, including their exit from the briquetting machine, passage through the drying furnace, transportation, storage, mixing with other components of the SAF mix, descent into the SAF during charging, and during the stoking operation within the SAF. The SiC formation test examines the SiC formation inside the briquettes during the heating process in an induction furnace. And the SiO reactivity test measures the reactivity of the carbonaceous material with SiO gas. This parameter is very important as it directly influences silicon yield in SAF operation.

5. SAF operation:

Finally, the briquettes that have passed quality control are used in the SAF operation for the carbothermic reduction of silica. In the furnace, the briquettes undergo a high-temperature reaction where the carbon source reduces the silica, producing silicon. This step is crucial to produce metallurgical-grade silicon, which is essential for various applications, including photovoltaic (PV) cells. In this work package, it was possible to produce metallurgical grade silicon both from briquettes made from pot scrap and briquettes made from silicon kerf.

3 REFINING ROUTES

From the three large (in volume) waste streams from the PV-silicon production process (mainly CZ-silicon pulling and wafer sawing), we have chosen to focus on two of the waste streams, namely quartz and silicon mix from discarded crucibles and pot scrap and the sawing dust from the wafer sawing process called kerf. The choice not to include graphite is built on previous results which are reported in the technical reports in the ICARUS-project:

- Low availability and insufficient homogeneity (WP1)
- Low reactivity (WP3)
- Hard to mill large volumes (WP1 and WP3)

According to the principle of circular economy, materials should be always kept at the highest possible level in a value chain. Therefore, it makes sense to try to reintroduce the waste streams intended as secondary raw materials at several points in the value chain. The goal is to find the optimized combination of pre-treatment needed and the level of reintroduction. In the following, we will present three different routes for reintroducing the material back to the PV-value chain, namely by:

- Carbothermic silicon production in Submerged Arch Furnace (SAF)
- Plasma melting of kerf
- Refining by directional solidification

3.1 Metallurgical route: Carbothermic silicon production in SAF

3.1.1 Method and procedure

Silicon is produced primarily through carbothermic reduction in submerged arc furnace (SAF). The process involves mixing quartz with carbon material and then heating the mixture to high temperatures (Figure 11). Carbon reduces silicon dioxide (quartz), producing molten silicon. The molten silicon is then cooled and solidified into blocks. The design of the furnace is an important part of this process. A pilot scale SAF furnace was constructed at SINTEF to meet the requirements of the ICARUS project. The furnace design is thoroughly reported in D3.2 Si-production screening experiments and will not be repeated here. Four campaigns were conducted. We demonstrated and investigated the use of self-reducing briquettes (NOSI and ICARUS) in the operation of SAF furnace for silicon production. NOSI briquettes are composed of pure carbon black (CB), pure quartz sand and sugar whereas the ICARUS briquettes are composed of pure carbon black, milled pot scrap (prepared by ReSiTech) and sugar. Both briquet types were with a C/SiO₂ mole ratio close to 3. The raw material inputs for the four SAF-tests are given in Table 7.

FIGURE 11: INDUSTRIAL SILICON PRODUCTION PROCESS⁸

TABLE 7: OVERVIEW OF RAW MATERIALS IN THE 4 SAF CAMPAIGNS

Campaigns	Materials
1	NOSI briquettes
2	NOSI briquettes + pot scrap lumps
3	ICARUS briquettes + pot scrap lumps
4	ICARUS briquettes + pot scrap lumps + kerf briquettes

As already mentioned, graphite was not included in our material selection, due to several reasons:

- The waste source is more diverse than expected and thorough sorting is therefore required. This makes graphite a less attractive raw material for the process, due to the added process step. The sorting will also result in a lesser amount available as raw material.
- The milling down of graphite delivered by NorSun turned out to be more time consuming than expected.
- Graphite has a low SiO-reactivity.

⁸ A. Schei, J. K. Tuset, and H. Tveit. Production of high silicon alloys. Tapir Trondheim, Norway, 1998.

Carbon black has different reactivities towards SiO depending on production method and purity. Due to logistical reasons and price, we were not able to obtain the same CB for the ICARUS briquettes as was used in the NOSI briquettes. The CB used in the NOSI briquettes have high enough reactivity⁹. The CB used in the ICARUS briquettes had a reactivity comparable to graphite, see Table 8 and D3.2 for details.

TABLE 8: SiO TEST¹⁰ RESULTS

Sample	Weight in (g)	Weight out (g)	Weight gain (%)
Graphite	8.325	12.448	49.5
Carbon black	9.46	13.115	38.6

The furnace operations and procedures consist of several steps: Lining heat-treatment, preheating the furnace, operating the furnace, preparing the charge material, conducting rodding and tapping operations. Figure 12 shows the furnace interior during operation, charging and rodding and Figure 13 shows tapping and tapped silicon melt. All steps are described in detail in D3.2. The main points are summarized here:

- In normal operation, the experiment is run in current control mode, and the process operator varies the current around 3 kA to achieve a 140–160 kW load. The voltage is measured and controlled by current, electrode position, and burden resistance. Typically, the voltage varies from 35 to 55 V. The electrode is gauged at the bottom position between some taps, and usually, the electrode's operational length is around 6 cm from the bottom. The electrode wear is expected to be 4-7 cm per tap, equivalent to 2-4 cm per hour.
- Charge preparation is done sequentially to adjust the carbon coverage between each tapping.
- After each tapping attempt, rodding is conducted to push material into the hot zone in the furnace.
- Tapping attempts were done at intervals of 300 kWh.
- Silicon melt was tapped and casted in air temperature and atmosphere.

SAF pilot-scale tests I and II were run directly after each other in the same campaign. Similarly, tests III and IV were run in a second campaign. The furnace was rebuilt for the second campaign, where the main improvements were a more heat resistant bottom (zirconia bricks replaced the chamotte bricks from test I and II) and higher purity lining and stoking equipment.

⁹ M. Piquand, INTERNSHIP REPORT: Development of new sustainable briquettes for silicon grade production, Sintef Industry (2023)

¹⁰ Lindstad, T., Gaal, S., Hansen, S. and Prytz, S., 2007. Improved SINTEF SiO-reactivity test. INFACON XI: Innovations in the Ferro Ally Industry, 1, pp.414-423.

FIGURE 12: SAF OPERATION. LEFT: FURNACE STATE. MIDDLE: CHARGING. RIGHT: RODDING

FIGURE 13: SAF OPERATION. LEFT: TAPPING. RIGHT: TAPPED METAL

3.1.2 Results and discussion

Both pilot-scale SAF campaigns produced silicon, but due to changes in furnace interior and, most notably, differences in CB reactivity, the results from Tests I and II are not directly comparable with results from Tests III and IV. The weight of the produced silicon per tapping and the purity of the silicon tapped are given in Table 9 for tests I and II and in Table 10 for tests III and IV. The silicon produced in these campaigns has purity and characteristics comparable to metallurgical grade silicon, specifically metal silicon 553, which currently has a market value of 1,585 USD per metric ton (excluding VAT). This is a significant finding in terms of purity for campaign 2, because 70% of the materials used in this campaign came from recycled pot scrap and recycled silicon kerf.

TABLE 9: WEIGHT AND PURITY OF THE TAPPED SILICON MEASURED BY ICP-MS AND XRF ANALYSIS FOR SAF I & II

Tapping #	1	2	3	4	5	6
Silicon weight (kg)	10.68	6.63	10.68	9.72	10.64	12.63
Purity (%)	97.8738	98.2707	98.4660	98.3890	98.3421	98.7944
XRF (%)	98.20	98.40	98.46	98.51	98.44	98.81

TABLE 10: WEIGHT AND PURITY OF THE TAPPED SILICON MEASURED BY ICP-MS ANALYSIS FOR SAF III & IV

Tapping #	1	2	3	4	5	6
Silicon weight (kg)	4.82	3.04	4.04	6.7	5.41	10.72
Purity (%)	98.4307	98.1651	98.0050	98.4681	98.7834	99.0514

It is important to note that in the second campaign, no successful tapping was made in Test III. All the six tapping in the second campaign (Table 10) happened in the second phase of the campaign during test IV. There are several possible reasons or combination of possible reasons for this result:

- There were unplanned stops to remove and replace damaged electrodes, which occurred more than once during the first phase of the campaign, significantly disrupted SAF operations. These frequent stops caused a loss of temperature in the crater zone, where the reaction between SiC(s) and SiO(g) to produce, liquid silicon is supposed to occur. Additionally, charges falling into the open space between the removal and replacement of electrodes further disturbed furnace operations. It is likely that these disruptions contributed to the lack of metal tapped during this phase of the campaign.
- Some of the self-reducing briquettes used in this campaign were not sufficiently strong to withstand the rigors of the charging process. It was observed that some briquettes disintegrated, which most likely hampered the reaction between the carbon and the pot scrap inside the briquettes to form SiC.
- The reactivity of the carbon black significantly influences the silicon yield in SAF operations. The carbon black used in this campaign had low reactivity, the same as that of graphite. This is believed to be one of the main reasons it was not possible to tap silicon during this phase.
- Another explanation could be that the process produced silicon deep in the bottom of the furnace, below the tap hole level, making it difficult to tap.

Excavation of the furnace after tests II and IV showed differences in both the physical appearance of the remaining briquettes in the furnace and the fixC analysis. The briquettes found during the excavation after test II showed that they can withstand the impact of mechanical handling and temperature during SAF operation. In addition to the physical observation of the furnace, fixed carbon content analysis of sample briquettes taken from different positions down the furnace

during excavation was conducted to better understand the process. The result of this analysis is shown in Table 11 for briquette samples taken from seven positions from top to bottom.

TABLE 11: FIXC ANALYSIS OF BRIQUETTES IN THE SAF FURNACE

Sampe	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Volatile matter (wt.%)	5.38	3.13	1.53	2.59	2.22	2.09	0.62
Ash content (wt.%)	66.00	70.98	68.59	94.82	72.13	97.34	95.37
Fix C content (wt.%)	28.62	25.89	29.88	2.59	25.64	0.58	4.01

It was observed that the fixed carbon content in the briquettes decreased going down into the inner reaction zone of the crater in the furnace. The carbon has been consumed by reacting with SiO₂ to form SiC in the outer reaction zone in the upper part of the charge. This is an important and beneficial finding because lack of free carbon is beneficial for formation of silicon. The silicon forming reaction taking place in the inner reaction zone is $\text{SiC} + \text{SiO} = 2\text{Si} + \text{CO}$. The equilibrium pressure SiO/CO is approximately 1/1 at 2000°C, that is the assumed temperature in the inner reaction zone. Free carbon in the inner reaction zone can react with SiC or SiO to form SiC and CO and thereby suppress formation of silicon. The other positive finding is that intact briquettes were found all the way through the charge down to the crater and inner reaction zone. Disintegration of the briquettes will hamper the reaction between carbon and quartz in the briquettes to form SiC and contribute to unwanted clogging and reduced porosity in the charge. Excavation of the furnace after test IV however showed that some of the briquettes had not withstood the impact of the SAF campaign similarly well as the briquettes from the first two tests.

CONCLUSIONS:

Despite the differences between the campaigns due to a rebuilt furnace and the challenges with no silicon tapped in test III, several conclusions can be made from the SAF campaigns.

- It is possible to produce agglomerates with high enough strength for SAF operations from CB, quartz sand or milled pot scrap, sugar and water by briquetting and subsequently heat treatment.
- Self-reducing briquettes with C/SiO₂ mole ratio close to 3 produces silicon in a SAF when carbon coverage is carefully optimized.
- Silicon production is increased by adding pot-scrap lumps.
- Silicon production is increased by adding kerf briquettes.
- Low SiO reactivity in graphite or low-reactivity CB makes silicon production challenging, but addition of pot scrap and/or kerf will increase the production slightly. We nevertheless recommend choosing CB with higher reactivity.
- Metallurgical silicon can be produced with 70% of the raw materials coming from recycled pot scrap and recycled silicon kerf.

FIGURE 14: OVERVIEW OF PROOF OF CONCEPT FOR THE METALLURGICAL ROUTE: CARBOTHERMIC SILICON PRODUCTION IN SUBMERGED ARCH FURNACE (SAF)

The four experimental campaigns demonstrated that metallurgical-grade silicon, comparable in quality to commercially available silicon, can be produced from recycled materials. These campaigns showed that recycled pot scrap has the potential to replace all the required virgin quartz in SAF operations. Additionally, the campaigns showed the significant role of silicon kerf in this process. These campaigns showed the feasibility of using recycled materials in silicon production, which could lead to more sustainable and cost-effective practices in the industry, see Figure 14.

3.2 Plasma refining of agglomerated Si-kerf

Silicon kerf is a significant waste product generated during the slicing of silicon ingots in wafer production. Recycling kerf back into the PV value chain requires innovative melting and purification processes, such as hydrogen plasma refining. This technology uses the properties of the ionized state of hydrogen gas to remove impurities. The recovered pure silicon can be reintegrated into the PV manufacturing process, reducing raw material costs and minimizing waste. However, kerf melting is challenging due to the small particle size and the silicon oxide layer, which constitutes a large share due to the large surface area compared to bulk silicon.

3.2.1 Method and procedure

Hydrogen plasma refining of agglomerated Si-kerf involves the following important steps to efficiently recycle silicon kerf waste.

1. Agglomeration of silicon kerf

The powdered silicon kerf particles need to be agglomerated into larger granules before undergoing further processing and refining. This agglomeration of Si kerf is achieved using spark plasma sintering (SPS) technology (Figure 15). The process employs a combination of pulsed direct current and uniaxial pressure applied to the powder within a die, resulting in rapid heating and sintering. The sintering time is approximately 30 minutes at 900-1000 degrees.

FIGURE 15: LEFT: SPARK PLASMA SINTERING. RIGHT: SINTERED SI-KERF

Electron Microprobe Analysis (EMPA) was performed on the sintered kerf samples to determine the material's structural properties and assess its homogeneity. The results of this analysis are presented in Figure 16. The results show that the sintered Si kerf has a very good porosity, but it has a less homogeneous density distribution.

FIGURE 16: EMPA ANALYSIS. LEFT: POROSITY. MIDDLE AND RIGHT: HOMOGENEITY

2. Hydrogen plasma refining

The plasma generation and refining process for silicon kerf involves the use of a plasma reactor where a mixture of argon and hydrogen gas is used to create ionized hydrogen plasma. This ionization is achieved by applying a high electric current, converting the hydrogen gas into a highly reactive ionized state. The agglomerated silicon kerf is then placed into a water-cooled copper crucible, where it is exposed to high temperatures and hydrogen plasma (Figure 17). The reactive hydrogen ions interact with the silicon kerf particles, effectively reducing silicon oxides and other impurities present in the kerf. The high-energy plasma breaks the chemical bonds in the impurities, transforming them into volatile compounds.

FIGURE 17: HYDROGEN PLASMA REFINING OF SI-KERF

To optimize the plasma refining process for silicon kerf, the plasma power is initially increased by adding hydrogen to the plasma gas. The electric current is gradually increased from 300 A to 400 A to increase the power. The plasma power is further increased until stable melt conditions are achieved. Once these conditions are met, the plasma power is gradually reduced to allow the solidification of the refined silicon. These operating parameters are illustrated in Figure 18. The refined silicon particles are then collected, cooled, and sampled for impurity analysis.

FIGURE 18: OPERATING PARAMETERS OF HYDROGEN PLASMA REFINING

3.2.2 Results and discussion

A sintered Si-kerf charge of 147 g was added to the copper crucible for the hydrogen plasma refining experiment. After refining, the weight of the sample was measured at 134 g, as shown in Figure 19. This weight change correlates with the removal of impurities through volatilization. Detailed chemical analyses, including LECO, ICP-MS, and XRF, were conducted on both the sintered and plasma-treated Si-kerf to evaluate the effectiveness of the refining process.

FIGURE 19: SI-KERF SAMPLE BEFORE AND AFTER THE PLASMA REFINING

LECO analysis was conducted to determine the carbon (C) and oxygen (O) content in the Si-kerf sample before and after the refining experiment. The result of this analysis is shown in Figure 20. As can be seen from the figure, the deoxidation and decarburization of silicon kerf is quite significant, especially for carbon.

FIGURE 20: LECO ANALYSIS BEFORE AND AFTER THE REFINING

Metallic and dopant impurities were assessed before and after the plasma refining experiment using ICP-MS analysis. The results of this analysis are presented in Figure 21.

FIGURE 21: ICP-MS ANALYSIS BEFORE AND AFTER THE REFINING

It can be seen from this figure that plasma refining of silicon kerf significantly reduced the concentration of metallic impurities such as aluminum (Al) and nickel (Ni). The impurity levels were reduced from 6079 ppmw to 57 ppmw for Al and from 163 ppmw to 4.6 ppmw for Ni. Similarly, the impurity concentrations for titanium (Ti) and zinc (Zn) decreased by 63% and 13%, respectively. On the contrary, the impurity concentrations for iron (Fe) and magnesium (Mg) increased after the refining process. This increase could possibly be due to contamination during the refining process or from the copper crucible.

The figure also shows the concentration of dopant impurities before and after the plasma refining process. It can be seen that the refining process completely removed the impurities boron (B) and gallium (Ga). On the contrary, the concentration of phosphorus (P) impurity increased. Further investigation is required to understand why this happened. Additionally, the XRF results show that the silicon purity increased from an initial 99% to 99.3% after the plasma refining process.

3.3 Directional solidification

A common method for silicon refining is directional solidification. Most impurities have a higher solubility in melted than in solid silicon. When silicon melts are solidified in a controlled way, the impurities will be pushed to the liquid phase. The final cast will consist of a large, purified part and a smaller part with high content of impurities (red zone), which will be discarded. There are two main technologies in common use today:

- 1) Directional solidification of multicrystalline silicon (mc-Si)
- 2) The Czochralski (CZ) method for monocrystalline silicon

Mc-Si is faster and less energy demanding to produce but contains extended defects such as grain boundaries and dislocation clusters. The produced ingot will cool down in the crucible and impurities present in the crucible or coating will diffuse back into the ingot, making a red zone at all sidewalls of the ingot. Furthermore, the final solidified fraction, which contains a high number of impurities is the top of the ingot. Some impurities in the top layer will have time to diffuse back into the ingot during cooling (back-diffusion). CZ-Si is a different process where a crystal is pulled out of the melt, leaving the last melt fraction with up-concentrated impurity levels in the crucible (pot scrap). This is a slower process and demands more energy but has no extended defects, better stirring in the melt and no back diffusion or in-diffusion of impurities from the crucible.

Traditionally, directional solidification of mc-Si is the method used for refining by segregation. Due to the better stirring of the melt in the CZ-process and the lack of in-diffusion and back diffusion, we will investigate if the CZ-process can be used for silicon refining as well. Due to the high impurity level (4N), we will not be able to pull a monocrystal, leaving us to deal with extended defects similarly to those in traditional mc-Si.

3.3.1 Method and procedure for mc-CZ-Si

The aim of CZ-crystal pulling is normally to produce a single crystal for wafer production, in this case, the aim is to investigate if the method can be used for a refining step. The CZ-crystal produced here was a multicrystalline ingot due to the high impurity content (4N). The Cz-process with stacking of feedstock into the crucible, melting, seed dipping and crystal pulling are shown in Figure 22. The final crystal is also shown. In total 38 kg ingot was pulled out of a charge of 50 kg.

FIGURE 22: FROM TOP LEFT: CHARGING, MELTING, SEED DIPPING, PULLING OF CZ-CRYSTAL FOR REFINING PURPOSES AND TAKING OUT THE FINAL CRUSTAL (MC-CZ)

FIGURE 23: PARTICLES FLOATING ON TOP OF THE MELT

Due to the high impurity content, particles were floating on top of the melt after the feedstock was fully melted, see Figure 23. These particles are believed to be silicon nitride needles and/or silicon carbide particles, since the saturation limit of N and C is most likely exceeded in the raw material. The melt was kept at melting temperature with rotating crucible, in 2.5 hours, until all visible particles were gone from the surface. The aim was to see if the particles could evaporate, but some particles were also observed to move to the crucible wall and may have stuck there. Before dipping the seed, all visible particles were gone from the surface and assumed evaporated or stuck to the crucible wall. After pulling the crystal, no tail was made, but the crystal was pulled directly out of the melt. This will reveal the solid/liquid interface shape.

3.3.3 Results and discussion

The ingot was cut, visually inspected and analyzed by Glow Discharge Mass Spectrometry (GDMS). The solid/liquid interface in the bottom (end) of the ingot is slightly concave, see Figure 24. The grain structure is columnar throughout the full length of the ingot, showing no sign of collapse of the growth front, which allow us to use the Scheil equation for segregation of impurities (presented in the discussion part).

FIGURE 24: IMAGE OF CROSS SECTION OF THE MC-CZ-INGOT

GDMS characterization was carried out to measure the impurity concentration in the Si feedstock and grown crystal. Figure 25 shows the impurity profile of the measured impurities (solid lines) and the impurity profiles as measured by Scheil equation. There is a large variation in concentration measured and not a good fit between the measured and calculated profiles. GDMS is a surface measurement technique, and the measured values should therefore not be interpreted as a bulk concentration. This shows therefore that local variations of the concentrations are present, due to particle formation and/or trapping and micro segregation of impurities at grain boundaries and other extended defects. This is thoroughly documented for traditional mc-Si ingots.

FIGURE 25: IMPURITY PROFILES AS MEASURED BY GDMS (SOLID LINES) AND CALCULATED BY SCHEIL EQUATION (DOTTED LINES)

To be able to conclude on the segregation effect, we use the values at 75% solid fraction. Table 12 shows impurity concentration in Si feedstock and impurity concentration in the grown crystal after 75% of solidification. The GDMS results show that most of the impurities got purified during the directional solidification process due to evaporation and effect of segregation. The low segregation effect of the doping elements (B and P) is due to their high segregation coefficient and is a fundamental challenge for this refining method. The doping elements are therefore normally treated in a separate purifying step.

TABLE 12: GDMS RESULTS: IMPURITY CONCENTRATION IN Si FEEDSTOCK AND IN CRYSTAL AFTER 75% OF SOLIDIFICATION FRACTION

Element	Impurity Concentration in Feedstock (ppb)	Impurity Concentration in crystal after 75% of Solidification (ppb)
B	20240	11051
Mg	160.704	20.906
Al	4125	349.16
P	11493	16014
Ca	39300	16758
Ti	38.426	3.6
Cr	2301	1443
V	152.708	84.7
Mn	121.147	53.5
Fe	6340	165.3
Ni	882.247	3357
Co	42.967	91.7
Cu	381.736	56.3
Mo	256.123	84.4
Cd	2122	1017
Sn	535.082	209.2
Sb	253.894	27.06
Pb	157.487	126.6
Bi	151.325	23.9

Figure 26 shows the percentage of impurity level in the crystal after 75% of solidification. The GDMS results show that the concentration of most of the impurities has decreased because of direction solidification process. The P, Ni and Co have shown higher concentration in the crystal than the Si feedstock. P has a high segregation coefficient, while Co and N may be due to particle formation or micro-segregation towards grain boundaries. Even though this study does not give a clear picture of the different impurity profiles, we conclude that CZ-pulling is a promising alternative for refining by segregation, but it has some of the same limitations as traditional mc-Si due to grain boundary and defect formation.

FIGURE 26: PERCENTAGE OF IMPURITY LEVEL AFTER 75% OF SOLIDIFICATION

3.3.3 Theoretical considerations

1. Purification by evaporation:

During the melting stage of the directional solidification process, the impurities which have low fusion temperature ($<1450^{\circ}\text{C}$) can easily volatile. Under the conditions of low pressure and high temperature during the melting process, the impurities which have higher vapor pressure than Si like Ca, Mg, Fe, Ti etc. start to evaporate from the free melt surface. Effective purification by evaporation is achieved for the easy vaporable impurities. The impurities which have high vapor pressure ($\text{Mg}>\text{Ca}>\text{Mn}>\text{Al}>\text{Cu}>\text{Fe}>\text{Ni}>\text{Ti}$) could effectively be removed during the melting process. However, the degree of vacuum pressure and the temperature of the melt determine the degree of volatilization of those impurities. The quantity of impurity that vaporizes from open unit area of melt is dependent on the equilibrium vapor pressure of the impurity (P), the molecular weight of the impurity (M), melting temperature (T), Gas constant (R), crucible diameter (d), condensing coefficient (α), and the height of walls of crucible above the melt (l) as shown in the expression below¹¹.

¹¹ Kekelidze, N., Tavadze, G., Khutsishvili, E., Gabrichidze, L., Mikaberidze, G., 2016. Effective segregation coefficients of impurities in Si Section B-Research paper Eur. Chem. Bull 5, 376–379. <https://doi.org/10.17628/ECB.2016.5.376>

$$m = \beta P \sqrt{\frac{M}{2\pi RT}}$$

where the coefficient β is calculated as

$$\beta = \frac{156.6\alpha}{1 + \alpha l d^{-1}}$$

2. Purification by segregation:

The ratio of the concentration of the solute in the crystal (C_s) to its concentration in the melt (C_L) is defined as equilibrium segregation coefficient k_o .¹²

$$k_o = \frac{C_s}{C_L}$$

The equilibrium segregation coefficient of most of the metals is (k_o) $\ll 1$ which indicates that the solubility of those metal impurities in Si solid is lower than Si melt. The crystal keeps on ejecting the impurities into the melt as the growth proceeds which keeps enriching the concentration of the impurity in the melt. As a result, the melted feedstock is purified during the directional solidification process. However, the efficiency of Si purification from impurities during directional solidification depends on the effective segregation coefficient. The segregation of the impurities can be expressed by Schiel's equation as follows¹³

$$C_s = k_{eff} C_o (1 - f_s)^{k_{eff}-1}$$

where C_s is the concentration in solid, C_o is the initial concentration in the liquid at the beginning of solidification, f_s is the solidification fraction, k_{eff} is the effective segregation coefficient. The effective segregation is dependent on the equilibrium segregation coefficient k_o , growth rate V , diffusion coefficient D and the solid-liquid interface boundary layer thickness δ as given below.

$$k_{eff} = k_o / (k_o + (1 - k_o) \exp(-V\delta/D))$$

$$\delta = 1.6 D^{\frac{1}{3}} v^{\frac{1}{6}} \omega^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

¹² Zhang, Y., Lei, Y., Ma, W., Wang, H., Hu, Y., Wei, K., Li, S., 2020. Preparation of high-purity Ti-Si alloys by vacuum directional solidification. *J Alloys Compd* 832. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.153989>

¹³ Friedrich, J., von Ammon, W., Müller, G., 2015. Czochralski Growth of Silicon Crystals, in: *Handbook of Crystal Growth: Bulk Crystal Growth: Second Edition*. Elsevier Inc., pp. 45–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63303-3.00002-X>

where δ is the boundary layer thickness, which is expressed in terms of the crystal rotation speed ω , the kinematic viscosity ν .

From the above expressions, it is evident that the effective segregation coefficient is greatly influenced by the process parameters such as the pull speed and the crystal rotation. If $V=0$, the effective segregation coefficient k_{eff} becomes the equilibrium segregation coefficient k_0 . Increasing the pull speed results in an increase in k_{eff} and the high pull speed leads towards 1. Hence the effective segregation coefficient lies in between k_0 and 1 ($k_0 < k_{eff} < 1$) during the solidification process. The variations in the pull speed and crystal rotation significantly influence the segregation of impurities. Due to segregation, the impurity pile-up in front of interface during the solidification. If the concentration of any one of the impurities exceeds its critical concentration (10^{17} - 10^{20} atoms/cm³) at any point in time during the solidification, it would lead to the onset of constitutional supercooling. As a result, the transition from planar to cellular growth takes place and this eventually ends up with the growth of multi-crystals.

The grown crystal had the transition from mono to multi from the beginning of the solidification which must be due to higher number of impurities in the Si melt. In multi crystals, the grain boundaries are the most important sinks for metal impurities, such as Fe and Al.¹⁴ Besides, the fast-growing dendrites due to supercooling or constitutional supercooling would trap the impurities that piled up in front of its interface¹⁵. If the growth is fast enough or faster than the speed of atomic diffusion, it will trap all solutions and become diffusion less solidification¹⁶. Moreover, the interactions between the impurities in the Si melt also needs to be included to concretize the purification mechanism.

¹⁴ Li, P., Wang, K., Ren, S., Jiang, D., Shi, S., Tan, Y., Wang, F., Khan Asghar, H.M.N. ul H., 2018. Microstructure and conversion efficiency of multicrystalline silicon ingot prepared by upgraded metallurgical grade silicon. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 186, 50–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2018.06.010>

¹⁵ Fujiwara, K., Chuang, L.C., Maeda, K., 2022. Dynamics at crystal/melt interface during solidification of multicrystalline silicon. *High Temperature Materials and Processes*. <https://doi.org/10.1515/htmp-2022-0020>

¹⁶ Herlach, D.M., 2014. Non-equilibrium solidification of undercooled metallic melts. *Metals* (Basel). <https://doi.org/10.3390/met4020196>

4 SUMMARY AND MAIN CONCLUSIONS

The following important conclusions can be made from the activities conducted in this task:

- The sources for secondary raw materials, silicon from kerf and quartz from crucibles are expected to be sufficient and their impurity levels are possible to handle for reintroduction into the PV-value chain.
- The recycled material from furnace insulation, graphite, is more uncertain due to inhomogeneous qualities, difficulties with milling and chemical reactivity.
- Agglomerates containing carbon black, quartz powder (virgin quartz sand or milled down crucibles and pot scrap) and sugar can be produced through briquetting with sufficient mechanical strength.
- Metallurgical grade silicon can be produced with 70% of the raw materials coming from recycled pot scrap and recycled silicon kerf by carbothermic reaction in a submerged arch furnace.
- Plasma refining seems a surprisingly promising refining method, particularly for p-type (both B and Ga-doped) silicon waste materials.
- Segregation refining by CZ-Si is possible.

